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THE GROUND REALITY OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The Government is contemplating on financial inclusion for the whole population. This is found in the policy decisions taken over the last years¹. These policies have been stimulated by the recommendations of the committees formed for strategies to promote financial inclusion and improving the health of rural financial structures. The financial inclusion has become the real buzzword today with the entire world re-orienting their strategies to achieve this end at the earliest²

Keywords: *Financial Inclusion, Inclusive Growth, No-frill Account, State Level Bankers Committee*

Introduction

The committees defined financial inclusion in the following ways:

Rajan Committee's Definition of Financial Inclusion

Financial inclusion, broadly defined, refers to universal access to a wide range of financial services at a reasonable cost. These include not only banking products but also other financial services such as insurance and equity products.

Objectives of the Study

1. To understand the concept of Financial Inclusion
2. To have insight into the various aspects of Financial Inclusion
3. To evaluate the measures taken by the Government of India and The Apex Bank for achieving financial inclusion and their impact
4. To identify the weaknesses in the implementation and suggest suitable remedies

Inclusive economic growth has been one of the priority agendas of the Government over the past decade. It is widely acknowledged that inclusive economic growth cannot be achieved without achieving financial inclusion for the two-thirds of India's population who are unbanked. In order to develop a strategy for achieving financial inclusion and, therefore, inclusive economic growth the GOI set up two committees to discuss issues and recommend action³. In 2006, the Committee on Financial Inclusion under the Chairmanship of

Mr C. Rangarajan was to suggest:

- A strategy to extend financial services to small farmers and other poor groups, including measures to regulate and ease procedures, reduce transaction costs and make the operations transparent⁴
- Measures including institutional changes to be undertaken to implement the strategy of financial inclusion.
- A monitoring mechanism to assess the quality and quantity of financial inclusion including parameters for assessing progress. In the following year, the Planning Commission constituted a High Level Committee on Financial Sector Reforms under the Chairmanship of Dr Raghuram G. Rajan, Professor, Graduate School of Business, University of Chicago. While its focus was on identifying emerging challenges in meeting the financing needs of the Indian economy as a whole, its recommendations also emphasized the need for and strategies for achieving financial inclusion⁵ Over three years have gone by since the reports of the committees were completed. This report reviews the progress of financial inclusion in the context of the recommendations, in light of the initiatives of the central government, RBI and NABARD for promoting financial inclusion. It analyses the initiatives of the authority and banks in promoting financial inclusion and explores issues, challenges and factors that hinder the progress of financial inclusion⁶

The Rangarajan Committee report had highlighted the extent of financial exclusion in terms of access to credit. Based on the analysis of the National Sample Survey Organisation (NSSO) data³ it was evident that:

- Around 52% of the farmer households (45.9 million out of 89.3 million households) do not access credit either from institutional or non-institutional sources,
- 73% of farm households do not have access to formal credit sources,
- Non-indebtedness was particularly high among marginal farmers (<1 hectare of owned land) with 70.6% not having access to formal/non-formal sources.

Across social groups exclusion was high among Scheduled Tribes (63.7%) and Scheduled Castes (49.8%)⁷

- Incidence of financial exclusion among all non-cultivator households (~59.6million households) was estimated at 78.2% which comprises of 78.8% of agricultural labourer households, 71.4% of artisans and 79.7% of other rural households.

The above data provides an idea of exclusion from access to credit, but as suggested by both committees, financial inclusion is a much broader term which includes reach to other financial services such as

savings, insurance, remittance and financial counselling. The main targets/strategies recommended for access to financial services for the excluded population were the following:

Providing financial services access to 50% of the total number of excluded households – around 55.8 million households by 2012.

- Credit to 11.15 million cultivator and non-cultivator households per annum (250 such households per bank branch per annum) with an emphasis on poor and marginal farmers.
- Opening of no-frills accounts for providing savings and payments services.
- Use of Business Facilitators (BF) and Business Correspondents (BC) for increasing the reach of financially excluded families by banks. This includes the creation of BC touch points in 600,000 villages across India.
- Promoting financial literacy by introducing financial terms in school books and educational programmes on television.
- Expansion of the bank branch network (commercial banks as well as RRBs) to the excluded/unreached districts.
- Furthering progress under the SHG Bank Linkage Programme (SBLP) of NABARD and maximising the coverage of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs)
- Use of technology and telecommunications for bringing down the cost of small transactions.
- Providing risk cover to the excluded population through micro-insurance.

Further, as stated in the latest annual report of RBI, even in the 26 districts that were declared 100% financially included by the State Level Bankers Committees (SLBCs), actual financial inclusion was not achieved to the full extent in all the districts. An RBI-sponsored study indicated that most of the accounts that were opened in these districts under the financial inclusion drive continued inoperative for various reasons and awareness with regard to no-frills accounts continued to be virtually non-existent in many districts. While there has been positive growth in covering excluded households, a vast majority of the population remains un-served.

The growth in the number of small credit (borrowable) accounts shows that:

- The number of such accounts of size ‘25,000 & below’ in the banking system rose from 36.8 million in 2004 to 39.2 million in 2009 – an increase of 2.4 million (just 6.5%).
- The number of borrowers with credit accounts of ‘less than 200,000’ increased from 61.9 million in 2004 to 95.8 million in 2009 – an increase of nearly 34 million (or 54.8%). It becomes apparent that for the coverage of those borrowing less than 200,000 to increase to at least 50% of the adult population in the next three years, the number of credit accounts would have to increase annually by at least 41.3%.

Conclusion

While the banks have made efforts to reach the poor sections of the population, there is still a long way to go before they can achieve their first target of covering 55.8 million excluded households and all villages with >2,000 population by 2012. So far, progress towards achieving this goal has been relatively limited and government efforts to promote financial inclusion in a serious manner will need an additional drive in order to help attain the necessary results.

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